

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14769475

Influence Of Inflation On Senior Secondary Schools Biology Students' Achievement In Bosso Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study Investigated Influence of inflation on senior secondary schools' Biology students in Niger state, Nigeria. A survey research design was employed for the study and the population for the study was 12,321 Biology students in all Government senior secondary schools in Niger state. 240 science students were selected through simple random sampling technique from 10 senior secondary schools in education zone B of the state, which formed the sample size for the study. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The research instrument was A researcher made 4- points scale Questionnaire, titled, Influence of inflation on senior secondary schools' Biology Achievement (IISSSBA) in Niger State, Nigeria. The reliability of the instrument was determined to be 0.70 using test retest method. The instrument was administered on the respondents in the 10 randomly selected schools in 2023/2024 academic session. Research questions were answered using simple percentage and frequency counts while hypotheses were tested through Chi Square statistical method. The findings of the study revealed that inflation has a serious impact on Biology Achievement of students. Based on the findings, two recommendations were made, among which is that, Niger State government should device means of cushioning the effect of inflation on educational stake holders by providing subsidized teaching and learning materials to schools and students for effective teaching and learning process which will result to positive influence on academic achievement.

Keywords: Inflation, Academic Achievement, Biology students

INTRODUCTION

Inflation is one of the major contemporary issues in Nigeria as the prices of essential goods and services are rising in an unimaginable and uncontrollable rate making it difficult for low and average income earners to afford essential goods and services in the country. Inflation refers to the general rise in the prices of goods and services thus leading to a fall in the purchasing power of a country's currency (Lipsey & Chrystal 1995). Inflation occurs when prices of goods and services expand more in proportion to the increase in the proportion of output (Shahid, 2010). Inflation can further be seen as a rise in the general price levels of goods and services over time and not prices of some specific set of goods or services, as in commodity inflation or core inflation, which is measured as the percentage rate of change of a price index. (Haq, 2008 in Ogundipe, & Egbetokun, 2013). Inflation may either be Demand-Pull inflation or Cost-Push inflation. Demand-Pull inflation is a type of inflation caused by persistent increase in aggregate demand over aggregate supply, thus the firms respond by raising prices and increasing their output (Sloman & Kevin 2007 in Egbedi & Edimeh, 2024). Effects of inflation are felt by everybody but mostly

hits the poor consequently increased their hunger and poverty, because of foodlessness or poor nutrition and a deteriorating standard of living; they become less likely to be productive and earn a living, they also become more vulnerable to diseases (CSOR, 2008 in Maku, & Adelowokan, 2013). During inflation, consumers need more goods and services for consumption purposes, Investors need more inputs for investment while government needs more goods and services to meet civil and military requirements of the country. Thus the aggregate demand comprises of consumption, investment and government expenditures. When the aggregate demand exceeds the value of aggregate supply at the full employment level, the inflationary gap arises. It can therefore be said, the excesses in aggregate demand over aggregate supply in the Nigerian economy to some extent has relationship with our inflation rate. Inflation influences the living standard of a country. When inflation rate increases, the price of all commodities also increases, this leads to a fall in the real value of money as too much money will be purchasing only few goods, reduction in the purchasing power of consumers and therefore, complicating the standard of living (Mihaljek, & Saxena, 2010). Though Nigeria has been in recession for a long time now, the recent fuel subsidy removal has further sloped the curve downwards. The dollarization of the Nigeria economy and inconsistent economic policies have led to devaluation of Naira and a collapse in the Nigerian economy which is characterized by hunger, unemployment and high cost of living (Perry, & Cline, 2013). High exchange rate of Naira to Dollar, insecurity, and infrastructural deficiency have further aggravated the inflation rate in the country, by increasing prices of imported raw materials, the cost of production, and the prices of commodities in the market. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, June 2024) reported that all measures of inflation rate rose in June 2024, as headline inflation increased to 34.2 percent in June 2024 from 22.8 percent in June 2023 and 34.0 percent in May 2024. inflation remains driven by currency depreciation, with the official exchange rate averaging N1471/US\$ in June compared to N769/US\$ in June 2023 and rising imported food inflation (36.4 percent y/y). Headline inflation remains dominantly driven by food inflation, which rose to 40.9 percent year-on-year, up from 40.7 percent in May 2024 and significantly higher than 25.3 percent in June 2023. Similarly, core inflation rose to 27.4 percent in June 2024, from 27.0 percent in May 2024 and 20.1 percent in June 2023 (NBS, June 2024). The average exchange rate in the parallel market is as high as N1700 per dollar in November 2024, in addition, most importers of food, raw materials, and machinery do not have adequate foreign currency from the official channels; as a result, they access the parallel market at a higher rate (Ashakah, 2022). Insecurity in the northern and Middle Belt regions contributes to high inflation in Nigeria as many farmers could not access their farms because of the fear of being kidnapped, raped, or killed by terrorists. Poor condition of Infrastructure also contributes to high inflation in Nigeria, most of the roads in Nigeria are not in good condition. According to the former Director-General of the Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (ICRC), Chidi Isuwa, Nigeria had about 200,000km of the road network. He stated further that only about 60,000km got paved; a large proportion of the paved road was in unacceptable poor condition due to insufficient investment and lack of adequate maintenance. Increase of transportation fare due to fuel subsidy removal has affected the cost of moving farm products from rural to urban areas which has resulted to high prices of food in the market. The erratic power supply is aggravating the high inflation problem in Nigeria as majority of businesses depend on self-generated power sources to power their operations. The high cost of running and maintaining power-generating plants enhances the problems of inflation, unemployment, and low growth rates in Nigeria (Ashakah, 2022). Impact of inflation on families has made it very difficult for many of them to have access to their basic necessities like good food, health care services and even good education as these goods and services are likely to go beyond their purchasing power. This drastic reduction in purchasing power of families compels them to resort to extra income generating activities which often times involves school age children. These activities interfere with learners' routine academic activities and result to lack of leisure time, productivity, better social activities poor physical health and poor academic achievements or total drop out of school. High inflation rate can also lead to a breakdown of the whole economy as money loses its value, teachers and other workers demand higher wages to cope with high cost of living and the more money is released into the system the more the prices of goods and services skyrocket (Perry & Cline, 2013). This is one of the major challenges faced by Nigerian economy today. Recently, Nigeria

Government announced the increment in minimum wage from 35% to 70%. But Nigerian workers are afraid as they express the uncertainty about what the new minimum wage could afford in the nearest future if prices of goods and services keep rising. Inflation rate in Nigeria is affecting all sectors of the economy, educational sector is mostly affected with increment in school fees, books and other teaching and learning materials; making it impossible for parents and even government to provide essential learning materials to students especially science students in senior secondary schools. Science education is often regarded as the key to success and the foundation of social, economic, and national growth on a global scale (Perry & Cline, 2013). Science Education is a systematic process in which learners get formal instruction in knowledge, attitudes, and skills that are essential for the change of individual and the society through hands on learning. The national education objectives for science education states that; for quality teaching and learning of science in Nigeria for sustainable development, the following objectives must be followed: (1). Basic literacy for functional living in society, (2). Basic concept and principles as a preparation for further studies (3). Essential skills and attitude for preparation for application of science for development and, (4). Stimulation of creativity. It can also be demonstrated empirically that Nigeria, among other countries, is unable to achieve the objectives of the national policy of science (Dike, 2015). So many factors are responsible for this among which is inflation and economic recession. Inflation has a severe impact on the provision of school facilities, money for education, and the working conditions of teachers, students, and families. When parents/guardians and instructors experience a decline in their purchasing power, it would impact negatively on their ability to provide books and educational materials to their wards, when parents can no longer afford to meet their children's financial needs in schools, especially in private schools, they are forced to take cheaper alternatives and most times inadequate materials are provided. Studying science without adequate learning materials contradicts the prescription of the national science education curriculum and is capable of affecting learning outcome which might result to fallen standard of education, with a multiplier effect on the economic growth of the nation. Most infrastructures in public schools are in deplorable conditions and no meaningful teaching and learning of science can take place where school buildings and laboratories are dilapidated. Inflation can also deny students access to good learning environment as parents, teachers' associations (PTA) and the government grapple with the effect of inflation by channeling their resources to provision of inevitable needs like food and health care services while schools' needs are put on hold. Importance of teaching materials, as well as the capacity of functional laboratories and libraries in schools, particularly for science subjects cannot be over emphasized (Okongo, Ngoa, Rop & Nyongesa, 2015). However, the high cost of teaching materials' as a result of the economic downturn brought about by high exchange rate, insecurity, corruption and fuel subsidy removal keeps them out of the grasp of majority of institutions. Yenle (2017) stated that high rate of inflation also affect government they have trouble disbursing grants, paying worker's compensation, buying books, subscribing to journals needed for effective delivery of the curriculum, training staff at workshops, conferences, and seminars, as well as keeping up with the rate of renovation of dilapidated buildings. The current rate of inflation in Nigeria also affects students' enrolment in the country, and Niger State in particular and may even undo recent progress achieved toward the elusive goal of universal primary school completion. Poor students have to forego schooling or miss some school days, and work outside the home as they may be obligated to make a living, this might be responsible for the noticeable high students' dropout and decline in academic achievement in the ministry of education promotion examinations in the recent past (Niger State Ministry of Education, 2024). Academic achievement is measured through a summative assessment process in schools. High academic achievement signifies effective teaching and learning process achievable through a conducive learning environment and provision of adequate number of desired learning materials. Science subjects like Biology requires a learning process which involves students' active participation, adequate teaching and learning materials, teachers' commitment in facilitating the learning process, field works and laboratory practical. If the economy is not favourable to parents, teachers, students and other educational stake holders achieving effective teaching and learning of Biology would be absolutely impossible and this will affect the academic achievement of students in the subject as academic achievement can be affected positively or otherwise by economic situation of a country or state. Consequently, it is imperative

to investigate the influence of inflation on senior secondary schools' Biology students' achievement in Niger State, Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine the influence of inflation on education, specifically;

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage	AA
Agree	165	77%	13%
disagree	75	23%	43%
Total	240	100	56%

1. To determine the Influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female Biology students in Niger State.
2. To determine the influence of inflation on academic achievement of male Biology students in Niger State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students in Niger State?
2. What is the influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female Biology students in Niger State?

Hypotheses for the Study

H0₁: There is no significant influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students in Niger State

H0₂: There is no significant influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female Biology students in Niger State

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was employed for the study and the population for the study was 12,321 Biology students in all government senior secondary schools in Niger state. 240 science students were selected through simple random sampling technique from 10 senior secondary schools in education zone B of the state, which formed the sample size for the study. Two research questions guided the study. The research instrument was A researcher made 4- points scale Questionnaire, titled, Influence of inflation on senior secondary schools' Biology Achievement (IISSSBA) in Niger State, Nigeria, with options of SA for strongly Agree, A, for agree, D, for disagree and SD for strongly disagree which were scored 4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was dully validated by 3 science educators and two experts in measurement and evaluation and the reliability was determined to be 0.70 using test retest method. The instrument was administered on the SS11 Biology students of the 10 randomly selected schools by the researcher in 2023/2024 academic session. Respondents were instructed to tick one of the options that was best appropriate to them in each of the items in the instrument. Data collected was analyzed using simple percentages, frequency counts and Chi Square statistical method. Third term Biology results which were collected from the examination officers of their respective schools served as the Biology Achievement scores of the respondents.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Answering research question one

1. *What is the influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students in Niger State?*

Table 1: Analysis of The Responses on Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of Biology Students in Niger State

Table 1 shows the frequencies and percentage of responses on influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students. A total of 165 students representing 77% of the sample size with average academic achievement of 13% agreed that inflation has negative influence on their academic achievements.

Answering Research Question 2: What is the influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female Biology students

Table 2: Analysis of The Responses on Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of Male and Female Biology Students in Niger State

Gender	N	Agree	AA	Disagree	AA	Mean difference
Male	126	85 (65%)	11%	41	23%	0.345
Female	114	80 (70%)	13%	34	21%	0.332
Total	240	165		75	44%	0.0013

Table 2 shows the frequencies and percentage of responses on influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female Biology students. A total of 85 students representing 65% of the total number of male with average academic achievement of 11% and mean score of 0.345 agreed that inflation has negative influence on their academic achievements, similarly, 80 female respondents representing 70% of the total number of female with average academic achievement of 13% and mean score of 0.332 agreed that inflation has serious negative influence on their academic achievement. The mean difference of 0.0013 indicates that inflation affects both male and female students equally.

Testing the Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students in Niger State

Table 3: Chi Square Analysis of Responses on The Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of Biology Students

Respondents	Observed	Expected	Df	X ^{2-cal}	X ^{2-crit}
Agree	143	165	1	6.84	1.32
Disagree	65	165			

Sig. 0.05

Table 3 shows Chi Square Analysis of Responses on The Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of Biology Students with a calculated value of 6.84 which is greater than the critical value of 1.32. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, hypothesis 1, which stated that there is no significant influence of inflation on academic achievement of Biology students was rejected which implies that inflation has significant influence on academic achievement.

Table 4: Chi Square Analysis of Responses on The Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of Male and Female Biology Students

Gender	Agree	Disagree	Observed	Expected	Df	X ^{2-cal}	X ^{2-crit}
Male	85	41	41	85	1	6.21	1.38
female	80	34	34	80			

Table 4 Shows Chi Square Analysis of Responses on The Influence of Inflation on Academic Achievement of male and female Biology Students with a calculated X² value of 6.21 which is greater than the critical value of 1.38. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, hypothesis 2, which stated that there is no significant influence of inflation on academic achievement of male and female students was rejected. This implies that inflation influences academic achievement of students

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings on influence of inflation on academic achievement of senior secondary schools' Biology students in Niger state, showed that inflation has a negative influence on academic achievement of

Biology students, this finding is in agreement with that of Abdullahi and Monika (April, 2017) which revealed that most teachers tried to adjust themselves to inflation situations by engaging in extra income generating activities, and also are subjected to receiving loans in order to meet up their expenditures, which consequently affected their job effectiveness and resulted to

Poor service delivery which led to decline academic performance of students. When teachers' wages are no longer able to sustain their essential personal and families' needs as a result of inflation, they do opt for multiple sources of income which eventually would divert their time, energy and focus from school activities, leading to unpreparedness for lessons and lack of adequate time for research and personal studies for effective lesson delivery, poor understanding and retention of the concept taught and poor academic performance of students.

Furthermore, the findings on influence of inflation on academic achievement based on gender revealed that, inflation impacts negatively on both genders' participation and concentration on class activities resulting in poor academic achievement of both male and female students. This finding is in agreement with that of (Niyi & Ukozor, 2023, September) which established that, inflation has led to male and female students' inability to participate actively in class activities poor academic achievement and increment in students drop out. The findings of Egbedi and Edimeh (2024) which confirmed that inflation and economic recession to a great extent deters students' concentration during lessons which also affect their understanding of lessons and led to poor academic achievement, while some students go to schools late and leave before official closing hours and most times are unable to complete assignments which also make them develop negative attitudes towards schools. Students from low and average income families are mostly affected by inflation as parents would not be able to cater for their schools' needs, they are often forced to take up part -time jobs and hawking of wares in order to make up for their parents' efforts. These activities interfere with their school time and activities leaving them with little or no time for school attendance, participation and concentration on class activities, and completion of take home activities which affects their learning outcome negatively, some often feel frustrated and may drop-out of schools.

Finally, the findings revealed that, there is a serious negative impact of inflation on academic achievement of both male and female student, this could be caused by inability of government to provide learning materials to students, particularly science learning materials like text books, science laboratory equipment and materials among other study materials. This finding aligns with that of (Niyi & Ukozor, 2023, September) which established that, inflation on university administration has led to an increment in the operational cost of running cost and reduction in academic performance of both male and female students. The findings of Jacob and Fredrick (2022, June) which revealed that inflation impacts on funding of secondary school education, affected the provision of instructional materials and infrastructure, school renovation and maintenance was difficult and negatively affected students' academic performance is also in line with the present findings. In times of inflation, both individuals and government are affected. Parents and guardians spend most of their income in feeding and health care services while secondary needs like educational needs are the foregone alternatives. Similarly, government spend large sum of money to acquire little educational facilities and this may result to inadequate provision of teaching and learning facilities in schools, dilapidated class rooms and unconducive learning environments with a resultant effect on academic achievement of students.

CONCLUSION

Inflation is a major threat to effective educational systems and is capable of thwarting the academic achievement of students, especially in science subjects. When prices of goods and services are beyond the reach of a common man, parents and teachers spend greater amount of their income in providing basic needs like food, health care services, accommodation and clothes. Most times, the government struggles to meet up with schools funding while teachers, and other low/average income parents could barely meet up with schools' fees, and learning materials of their wards, hence, students/pupils are forced to carry out economic activities for additional income which may interfere with their academic activities and lead to

decline in academic achievements particularly in science subjects like Biology which requires utilization of instructional aids, practical experience and active participation of learners in the learning process.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Niger State government should device means of cushioning the effect of inflation on educational stake holders by providing subsidized teaching and learning materials to schools and students for effective teaching and learning process which will result to positive influence on academic achievement.
2. Male and female students should utilize the available learning resources to maximize their potential which will help improve their academic achievement despite the high rate of inflation.

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